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Research Article

INCIDENCE OF TYPICAL ANATOMICAL CHANGES IN
EXTRAHEPATIC BILIARY TRACT IN PATIENTS PLANNED
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Abstract:

Aim: A cross-sectional study was performed to determine the frequency of typical anatomical changes in extrahepatic biliary tract in patients undergoing elective cholecystectomy.

Place and Duration: In the Surgical Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Method: A total of 136 patients were enrolled in the study who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Written consent was obtained from the patient. All patients underwent cholecystectomy by a general surgeon or senior registrar, according to hospital protocols with over 2 years of experience after the post-fellowship.

Results: The average age of patients was 40.9 ± 12.3 years, and the ratio of men to women was 1: 7.5. Anatomical variability was observed in 13 (9.6%) of 136 cases. Moynihan's hump was seen in 8 (5.9%) cases while Accessory cystic artery was noted in 5 (3.7%) cases.

Conclusion: Anatomical variability in 136 cases (9.6%), Moynihan's hump (5.9%) and an additional cystic artery (3.7%) were observed in this study. These anatomical variants tend to be injured during cholecystectomy, and the result of cholecystectomy depends on a clear understanding of normal anatomy and the variants duct.

Key words: cholelithiasis, Anatomical variation, Moynihan's hump, ancillary cystic artery,

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INTRODUCTION:

Cholelithiasis is common worldwide, and the symptoms range from mild to severe upper stomach pain, nausea, vomiting and indigestion¹⁻². Women develop gallstones twice as often as men. Cholecystectomy refers to the surgical removal of the gallbladder. Open cholecystectomy involves surgical removal of the gallbladder by means of an incision in the upper right quadrant of the abdomen. Offers a complete cure for a surgical disease³⁻⁴. The introduction of laparoscopic technique (using 4 very small ports instead of one large incision) in the 1980s completely changed and changed the approach to gallbladder disease. In recent years, additional changes have been made to laparoscopic techniques, of which the most important is single-laparoscopic surgery (SILS), which uses a small incision around the navel. Despite the excellent visualization of the gallbladder and surrounding structures during laparoscopy, sudden anatomical changes can be worrying for surgeons⁵. There are many studies indicating that the typical anatomy of a hepatobiliary tree manual occurs only in 60-80% of the population. Due to the routine use of laparoscopic technique, there is sufficient evidence that there is a higher incidence of changes in the bile ducts, cysts and vessels in structures adjacent to the gallbladder⁶. Among total anomalies of 14 cases, the Moynihan's hump (6%), accessory cystic artery (6%), double cystic duct (1%) and Long cystic duct (1%) were the total encountered variations. Although there are many pre-operative imaging and diagnostic tools to assess liver and bile duct anatomy, both are unreliable and very expensive for most of our country's population. Small changes in anatomy can cause significant iatrogenic damage to adjacent structures, and therefore can increase patient morbidity and even mortality, as well as significantly increase treatment and hospitalization costs⁷⁻⁸. The rationale for the study is to estimate the size of additional hepatic bile tree anomalies, because there is a lack of literature at this level. In addition, in selected cases intraoperative cholangiography was performed with anatomical changes during surgery⁹. Therefore this study is planned to estimate the exact magnitude of extra hepatic biliary tree. Based on the results of the study some strategies could be made to avoid iatrogenic injury to the underlying structures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

136 patients admitted to the Surgical Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020 for elective cholecystectomy, participated in this cross-sectional study. Patient inclusion criteria, i.e. > 18 years and <75 years, all male and female patients were evaluated with cholelithiasis cases for more than a month and with ASA status I and II. Exclusion criteria were gallbladder abscess, acute pancreatitis, obstructive jaundice, and gallbladder cancer. After completing the entire task of surgery and anesthesia, patients were admitted to the outpatient clinic (OPD). Prior to the operation, the patient received written and informed consent. All patients were asked to take a bath in the morning, a shaved area in the operating room, and skin prepared according to standard aseptic surgery protocols. All patients underwent cholecystectomy by a general surgeon or senior recorder, according to hospital protocols with over 2 years of experience after the scholarship. Basic variables, i.e. age, gender and results, i.e. anatomical variants of additional hepatic bile ducts, Moynihan's humpback and ancillary cystic artery (operative definition) were recorded. Data were entered and analyzed in SPSS version 16. Descriptive statistics were reported for mean $\pm$ SD for patient age, disease duration and surgeon experience. Frequencies and percentages are presented by gender, open or Laposcopic cholecystectomy, and anatomical variations, including Moynihan's humpback and additional cystic artery. Impact modifiers were controlled by age, sex, type of surgery, and duration of illness.

RESULTS:

A total of 136 cases of cholelithiasis were included in the study. The mean age of patients was 40.9 ± 12.3 . The minimum age was 21 years, the maximum age was 71 years, and the range was 50 years. Most patients were between 36 and 79 years of age (58.1%). Out of 136 patients, 16 (11.8%) were male and 120 (88.2%) were female with male to female ratio was 1: 7.5. While 94 (69.1%) of 136 cases of cholelithiasis were subjected to laparoscopic cholecystectomy, 42 (30.9%) open surgery were performed as shown in Figure 2. The average surgeon experience was 5.9 ± 2.3 years.

Figure 1 : Anatomical variation seen during cholecystectomy (n = 136)

Anatomical variation was not observed in 13 (9.6%) of 136 cases. Fig. 1. Moynihan's hump was observed in 8 cases (5.9%) and cystic artery in 5 cases (3.7%). Table 1

Table 1: Types of anatomical variation seen during cholecystectomy (n = 136)

Types of variations	Number of cases	Percentages
Moynihan's hump	8	5.9%
Accessory cystic artery	5	3.7%

Stratification was done with regards to gender, age, type of surgery and duration of disease to see the effect of these on outcome. Anatomical variation was high in female 12 (10%), in age between 36 – 50 years 9 (11.4%), in laproscopic cholecystectomy 11 (11.7%) and in patients having disease more than five years 10 (10.5%). Table-2.

Table 2: Distribution of accessory cystic artery with respect to gender, age, types of surgery experience of surgeons and duration of disease (n = 136)

	Total	Accessory cystic artery n = 5	Percentages
Gender Male			
	16	0	0.0%
Female	120	5	4.2%
Age			
21 - 35	36	1	2.8%
36 - 50	79	3	3.8%
≥ 50	21	1	4.8%
Type of surgery			
Laproscopic	94	3	3.2%
Open	42	2	4.8%
Duration of Disease (years)			
< 5	41	1	2.4%
≥ 5	95	4	4.2%

Moynihan's hump index was 7 (5.8%) in women, 5 (6.3%) aged 36-50, laproscopic cholecystectomy 6 (6.4%) and over five years of disease 6 (6.3%).

DISCUSSION:

Laparoscopic and open cholecystectomy are two surgical options for symptomatic gallstones with a cure of up to 95%. The success and safety of open and laparoscopic cholecystectomy depends on basic information about normal anatomy and additional biliary system, and typical variants of the cystic channel⁹⁻¹⁰. The bile duct has more abnormalities in the cystic region in a space of 1 cm - 13 cm compared to other parts of the body. To prevent bile complications during open cholecystectomy, it is important to carefully examine the Calot triangle and precisely define the additional hepatic biliary tree¹¹⁻¹².

The average age of patients in this study was 40.9 ± 12.3 years. The minimum age is 21 years and the maximum is 71 years. There were 16: 11.8% men and 120 (88.2%) women with a ratio of men (women) of 1: 7.5. The Sindh Pakistan study examined 300 cases of cholelithiasis and reported similar distribution by sex and age¹²⁻¹³.

Anatomical variety of extrahepatic biliary tree has been the subject of numerous studies, the reported incidence of congenital anomalies is from 1.6 to 47.2%. In this study, anatomical variability was observed in 9.6% of cases, Moynihan hump in the case (5.9%) and ancillary cystic artery in the case (3.7%). In the local study, total abnormalities were reported in 14 cases, Moynihan's humpback whale (6%), additional cystic artery (6%), double cystic channel (1%) and anatomical variability in 14% of cases. In another local study, surgical results revealed differences in 61 (20.33%) patients, mainly in the cystic artery (10.67%), in the cystic cyst (4.33%), in the right hepatic artery (2.67%) and gallbladder (2%). Other studies report the incidence of cystic cysts in the range of 1 to 30%. In a study conducted in Iraq, anatomical changes were found in 18% of cases, among these changes it was observed that Moynihan's hump (4%) was observed in cases. According to Benson and Page, the Moynihan hump incident ranged from 5 to 15%¹³. Carol et al. The incidence ranges from 6 to 16% in the study reported by. From 35 cases of Johnston and Anson 120 only 1 case was found with Moynihan's humpback whale (2.86%). In post-mortem studies, Bergamaschi and colleagues found that the Moynihan hump is one of the third contents of the Calot triangle in 12.9% of cases. Prithi et al. Moynihan hump was found in 1 case (1.6%). In a study by Jansirani D et al. Moynihan found a hump in 5% of cases. These results are consistent with this study. During cholecystectomy, arterial abnormalities should be identified to prevent arterial bleeding and thus iatrogenic changes¹⁴. The most dangerous abnormality is the tortuous course of the common hepatic artery or right hepatic artery prior

to the onset of a cyst known as "rotation or Moynihan caterpillar hump." The most important is the short cystic artery originating from the looped right hepatic artery and most susceptible to trauma during cholecystectomy. In this study, a short cystic artery was observed in 1.67% of cases. In 15% of cases, the right hepatic and cystic artery passes before the common hepatic and cystic duct, and the additional cystic artery is in 20%. The differences in the course of cystic artery in this series were such that the artery before the cystic canal in 2.67% passed in the lateral segment in 1.33%, and to the right from the cystic canal in 0.67%. Changes in the number of cystic arteries, such as double cystic artery, occur in 15% of cases, while single cystic artery occurs in 85% of cases¹⁵. The results of this study suggest that congenital anomalies and anatomical variations of extra-hepatic biliary tree are not common, but their clinical significance and, if any, may be surprising. Therefore, every surgeon should assess these abnormalities during laparoscopic cholecystectomy to prevent accidental cord jamming, canal damage, narrowing, and bleeding problems. Knowledge of these abnormalities will reduce morbidity, conversion and retesting in these patients.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, anatomic variability was observed in 136 cases (9.6%), Moynihan's hump (5.9%) and an additional cystic artery (3.7%).

We find that anatomical changes are not uncommon in our environment. Both the Moynihan humpback whale and the additional cystic artery are common anatomical variants in our patients. It is recommended that those surgeons doing cholecystectomy should repeatedly refresh their knowledge of normal anatomy as well as those of variants of biliary tree.

REFERENCES:

1. Schendel J, Ball C, Dixon E, Sutherland F. Prevalence of anatomic landmarks for orientation during elective laparoscopic cholecystectomies. *Surgical Endoscopy*. 2019 Sep 26;1-5.
2. Singh H, Singh NK, Kaul RK, Gupta A, Tiwari S. Prevalence of anatomical variations of cystic artery during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *International Surgery Journal*. 2019 Sep 26;6(10):3781-5.
3. Pesce A, La Greca G, Ultimo LE, Basile A, Puleo S, Palmucci S. Effectiveness of near-infrared fluorescent cholangiography in the identification of cystic duct-common hepatic duct anatomy in comparison to magnetic resonance cholangio-pancreatography: a preliminary study. *Surgical endoscopy*. 2019 Oct 9:1-7.

4. Rhaiem R, Piardi T, Renard Y, Chetboun M, Aghaei A, Hoeffel C, Sommacale D, Kianmanesh R. Preoperative magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography before planned laparoscopic cholecystectomy: is it necessary?. *Journal of Research in Medical Sciences: The Official Journal of Isfahan University of Medical Sciences*. 2019;24.
5. Kramer S. *Clinical findings and prognostic factors for dogs undergoing elective versus non-elective cholecystectomies for gallbladder mucoceles* (Doctoral dissertation).
6. Luo Y, Yang T, Yu Q, Zhang Y. Laparoscopic Ultrasonography Versus Magnetic Resonance Cholangiopancreatography in Laparoscopic Surgery for Symptomatic Cholelithiasis and Suspected Common Bile Duct Stones. *Journal of Gastrointestinal Surgery*. 2019 Jun 15;23(6):1143-7.
7. Banchini F, Capelli P. Left Side Gallbladder: Clinical and Anatomical Implication. In *Bile Duct 2020* Apr 27. IntechOpen.
8. Cheruiyot I, Nyaanga F, Kipkorir V, Munguti J, Ndung'u B, Henry B, Ciocchi R, Tomaszewski K. The prevalence of the Rouviere's sulcus: a meta-analysis with implications for laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Clinical Anatomy*. 2020 Apr 13.
9. Alshareefi LA, Ali MA, Metib NJ, Jasim M. The Frequency of Gall Bladder Pathology in Consecutive 576 Cholecystectomies. *Karbala Journal of Medicine*. 2019;12(1):4154-62.
10. Kurahashi S, Komatsu S, Matsumura T, Fukami Y, Arikawa T, Saito T, Osawa T, Uchino T, Kato S, Suzuki K, Toda Y. A novel classification of aberrant right hepatic ducts ensures a critical view of safety in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *SURGICAL ENDOSCOPY AND OTHER INTERVENTIONAL TECHNIQUES*. 2020 May 6.
11. Lehrskov LL, Westen M, Larsen SS, Jensen AB, Kristensen BB, Bisgaard T. Fluorescence or X-ray cholangiography in elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a randomized clinical trial. *British Journal of Surgery*. 2020 May 1;107(6):655-61.
12. Paramythiotis D, Moysidis M, Rafailidis V, Bangeas P, Karakatsanis A, Kalogera A, Michalopoulos A. Ducts of Luschka as a rare cause of postoperative biloma. MRCP findings. *Radiology case reports*. 2019 Oct 1;14(10):1237-40.
13. Esposito C, Corcione F, Settini A, Farina A, Centonze A, Esposito G, Spagnuolo MI, Escolino M. Twenty-Five Year Experience with Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in the Pediatric Population—From 10 mm Clips to Indocyanine Green Fluorescence Technology: Long-Term Results and Technical Considerations. *Journal of Laparoendoscopic & Advanced Surgical Techniques*. 2019 Sep 1;29(9):1185-91.
14. McVeigh G. Gall Bladder Carcinoma. In *Histopathology Reporting 2020* (pp. 115-121). Springer, Cham.
15. Tokuyasu T, Iwashita Y, Matsunobu Y, Kamiyama T, Ishikake M, Sakaguchi S, Ebe K, Tada K, Endo Y, Etoh T, Nakashima M. Development of an artificial intelligence system using deep learning to indicate anatomical landmarks during laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Surgical Endoscopy*. 2020 Apr 18:1-8.